

Effect of moisture on human tissue impedance measurement using textile electrodes

E. Petrovs¹, A. Okss², and A. Katashev¹

¹ Mechanical and Biomedical Engineering Institute, Riga Technical University, Riga, Latvia

² Institute of Architecture and Design, Riga Technical University, Riga, Latvia

* Corresponding author, email: Aleksejs.Katasevs@rtu.lv

Abstract: The effect of skin surface moisture on the apparent foot's electrical impedance, measured using textile electrodes, was studied. The sweating of the foot was simulated by spraying saline on the surface of animal cadaver phantom (porcine trotters). The electrical impedance was measured by 4-ptobe (Kelvin) methods. The results demonstrated that the impedance of the tissue expectedly decreases as the level of moisture increases. At the same time, the impedance phase angle does not depend on the surface moisture level. This implies that use of phase angle for foot tissue monitoring could compensate for the effect of foot sweating.

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I. Introduction

Diabetic neuropathy is a wide-spread disease, affecting about 130 million people worldwide [1]. The typical complication of this condition is diabetic foot ulcer, that is caused by elevated plantar pressure in persons, having diabetes. The neuropathy – related reduced sensitivity suppresses patient's ability to feel pain and foot overload, thus the conditions for excessive tissue damage are created.

Various technical solutions were proposed and will be proposed in future to help diabetic patients to note feet overload and take appropriate measures to prevent tissue damage [1]. Electrical impedance analysis was applied for the analysis of diabetic patient foot skin [2], monitoring of diabetic foot ulcer healing [3], exploration of the skin hydration process [4]. The smart sock prototypes, designed to monitor foot impedance, were proposed, too [5].

On the other hand, development of smart and functional textile enabled use of textile electrodes for bioimpedance measurements [6]. Textile electrodes offer several advantages: they are soft, can be easily embedded in socks design and therefore provide a high level of comfort for the patients. Nevertheless, use of sock - embedded textile electrodes could be compromised by the foot sweating. The increased moisture of the foot skin could cause an expectable decrease in the apparent foot tissue impedance, as the conductivity of soaked electrodes could increase.

The alteration of the skin impedance due to change in human physiological condition is well known as galvanic skin response [7]. The moistening of the skin surface because of sweating was mentioned as one of the processes underpinned changes in skin impedance. Up to the authors' knowledge, no one tried to separate the effect caused by superficial skin moistening from the effect, related to the change of the intrinsic conductance/reactance of the skin and superficial tissues, no matter was it caused by skin

hydration (like in [4]) or any other process. Therefore, the objective of the present research is to explore how the moistening of the skin superficial level alters apparent tissue impedance, measured using textile electrodes.

II. Material and methods

The measurements were done using porcine cadaver phantom (porcine trotters): commercial livestock is already widely used as a model tissue for electric impedance measurements [4, 8]. The electrodes were knitted from the cotton yarn with addition of silver-coated Shieldex™ conductive yarn. The resistance of the electrodes (measured along long side) did not exceed 5 Ohm. Four-electrode Kelvin probe scheme was employed. The setup is presented in Fig.1.

Figure.1: Experimental setup with porcine cadaver and four textile electrodes.

The measurement circuit enabled injection of the current via outer electrodes, measurement of the amplitude voltage over internal electrodes, amplitude current, flowing through the phantom, and phase delay between voltage and current. The current frequency was altered in the range 10 – 100kHz. For each frequency, the module of electrical impedance and phase angle were calculated.

The moistening of the skin was provided by spraying saline over the phantom surface. The amount of moisture was estimated by the mass of sprayed liquid.

III. Results and discussion

Fig.2 represents the electrical impedance and phase angle spectra for different moisture levels.

Figure 2: Phantom electric impedance (a) and phase (b) spectra for different moistening levels.

The obtained results are, in general, consistent with the previously demonstrated data [4] and theoretical prognosis. Indeed, with increment of the skin surface moisture, the total apparent impedance decreases, as expected, because the saline level “shortcut” the impedance of the tissue itself. At the same time, the phase of the impedance does not depend so much on the moisture – it does not demonstrate smooth tendency and either does not change much or changes chaotically when moisture increases.

The electrical impedance of the phantom was represented by the following equivalent circuit (Fig.3), where R_0 is related to the resistance of the moist layer.

Figure 3. Phantom's equivalent circuit.

Equivalent circuit allow to express the phantom impedance as:

$$|Z| = R_0 \sqrt{\frac{1 + \omega^2 R^2 C^2}{1 + \omega^2 (R_0 + R)^2 C^2}} \quad (1)$$

Parameters R_0 , R and C were estimated by fitting equation (1) and experimental curves (Fig.2b) using least squares method and iterative approach (MS Excel Solver tool). The resulting parameters are presented in Fig.4.

Figure 4. Estimation of the parameters of phantom's equivalent circuit.

The estimation shows that moisture most affects resistance R_0 , as it in part represents the resistance of surface moisture layer. At the same time, the resistance R , that is related to the intrinsic resistance of the cells, is less susceptible to moisture. The increase of the capacitance C could be explained by hydration of the skin, where liquid “fill” capacitive gaps between cells membranes

IV. Conclusions

The obtained data suggest that the phase of the tissue electrical impedance and resistance R of the equivalent circuit (Fig.3) will be less sensitive to the sweating of the foot, therefore future methods to monitor foot electrical impedance could be based on the measurement of these parameters

AUTHOR'S STATEMENT

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